

Thiothiazanes—A Study of Ethanol Interaction

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In our earlier communication¹, the product obtained by the treatment of 2-thiono-4-oxo-1, 3-thiazane-5-acetic acid (I), with ethyl alcohol in presence of hydrogen chloride was shown to be the corresponding ester V. For comparison V was synthesised independently from diethyl bromomethylsuccinate and ammonium dithiocarbamate followed by acid cyclisation² of the intermediate ester VI. Further exploration of esterification of compound I has revealed that if the esterification mixture was maintained at room temperature (30-35°C) for 24 hrs, only compound V is formed (TLC, I.R. and U. V. (309.5 and 259 m μ), but when the reaction mixture was kept for a prolonged duration (48 hours or more) an additional spot was also observed on TLC. The identity of this minor product was established as VI from its TLC behaviour, I.R. (3390, 3225 and 1010 cm⁻¹) and U.V. (276, and 243 m μ) spectra; this open chain ester could have resulted by the cleavage of amide linkage of V. However, efforts to isolate compound VI in analytically pure form, through distillation or column chromatography led to the formation of cyclised product V.

The change in U.V. spectrum in absolute ethanol of I, on standing, provided evidence for the formation of open chain product even in the absence of mineral acid. This led us to a detailed study of the absorption spectra of I, II & III in ethanol solution. In all the three cases, it was noticed that the ring fusion did take place, and the products formed respectively had spectra identical with the corresponding β -dithio-carbamylalkyl acid esters (IV).

1. Mamdapur, Choughuley and Chadha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1966, 43, 37.

*The mention of acid cyclisation step was not made in Ref. 1.

Garaway² has also reported the rupture of the amide bond in the case of 3-substituted 2-thiono-4-oxo-1,3-thiazane derivatives on ethanol interaction.

The ring fission rates of the three thiothiazanes were studied as follows:

Solutions of known molar concentrations ($4-6 \times 10^{-5}M$) in absolute alcohol were maintained at $27 \pm 0.2^\circ$ in a thermostatically controlled bath. Aliquots were withdrawn at known intervals and the optical density measurements made on Zeiss Recording Spectrophotometer RPQ-20A. The 310 m μ wavelength region was chosen for these measurements as only the thiothiazanes showed absorption in this region and not the open chain esters (IV).

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

The plot of log O.D. values vs time in minutes give straight lines as shown in Fig. 1 from which it is concluded that the reaction is of first order with respect to the solutes I, II and III.

FIG. 3

The velocity constants were calculated from the slope of the plot log O.D. vs time and are given in Table I.

2. Garaway, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 4072.

TABLE I

Rate constants for the ethanolysis of thiothiazanes I, II and III at $27 \pm 0.2^\circ\text{C}$

Compound	Rate constant (10^{-6} sec^{-1})
I	60.90
II	6.04
III	10.92

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